

FEATURES OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASSISTANCE IN EXTREME SITUATIONS

Askarova Nargiza Abdivalievna¹,
Ibragimova Nozima²

¹ Senior Lecturer of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology,
² Tashkent Medical Academy, Student of Medical - pedagogical faculty.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6334738>

Annotation. When providing psychological assistance to people who have been in extreme situations, one very important provision should be taken into account - a real disaster occurs when the effect of the elements ends and assistance to the victims begins.

Keywords. psychological help, critical situation, delirium, hallucination, apathy, stupor, hysteria, tension, stress, fear.

Already in the first approximation to the characterization of the scope and content of this concept, in abstraction from various positions, studies and views on the problem, it is not difficult to imagine the main thing: the content of psychological assistance is to provide emotional, semantic and existential support to a person or community in difficult situations that arise during their personal or social existence.

Any crisis events - natural disasters, accidents, catastrophes, armed conflicts - lead to social and psychological consequences that disrupt the normal course of people's lives. When a threat arises in front of a person, his natural reaction to such a change in his usual environment is stress - a state of physical or psychological excitement. Emergency psychological assistance to the population should be based on the principle of intervention in the surface layers of consciousness, that is, on working with symptoms, and not with syndromes

Delusions and hallucinations. A critical situation causes powerful stress in a person, leads to strong nervous tension, disrupts the balance in the body, and negatively affects health in general - not only physical, but mental too. This can exacerbate an already existing mental illness. The main signs of delirium include false ideas or conclusions, in the fallacy of which the victim cannot be dissuaded. Hallucinations are characterized by the fact that the victim experiences a sensation of the presence of imaginary objects that do not currently affect the corresponding sense organs (hears voices, sees people, smells, etc.).

In this situation:

1. Contact medical workers, call a psychiatric emergency team.
2. Before the arrival of specialists, make sure that the victim does not harm himself or others. Remove objects that are potentially dangerous from it.
3. Isolate the victim and do not leave him alone.
4. Speak to the victim in a calm voice. Agree with him, do not try to convince him. Remember that in such a situation it is impossible to convince the victim.

Apathy may occur after a long hard, but unsuccessful work; or in a situation where a person suffers a serious setback, ceases to see the meaning of his activity; or when it was not possible to save someone, and a loved one who got into trouble died. A person can be in a state of apathy from several hours to several weeks.

The main signs of apathy are:

- indifferent attitude to the environment;
- lethargy, lethargy;
- slow, with long pauses, speech.

In this situation:

1. Talk to the victim. Ask him a few simple questions: "What is your name?"; "How do you feel?"; "Do you want to eat?".
2. Escort the victim to a place of rest, help to get comfortable (be sure to take off your shoes).
3. Take the casualty by the arm or put your hand on his forehead.
4. Give the victim the opportunity to sleep or just lie down.
5. If there is no opportunity to rest (accident on the street, in public transport, waiting for the end of the operation in the hospital), then talk more with the victim, involve him in any joint activity (walk, go for tea or coffee, help others who need help) .

Stupor. Stupor is one of the most powerful defensive reactions of the body. It comes after the strongest nervous shocks (explosion, attack, brutal violence), when a person has spent so much energy on survival that he no longer has the strength to contact the outside world. The main signs of stupor are:

- a sharp decrease or absence of voluntary movements and speech;
- lack of reactions to external stimuli (noise, light, touch, tweaks);
- "freezing" in a certain position, numbing, a state of complete immobility;
- possible tension of individual muscle groups.

In this situation:

1. Bend the victim's fingers on both hands and press them to the base of the palm. The thumbs should be outward.
2. With the tips of the thumb and forefinger, massage the affected points located on the forehead, above the eyes exactly in the middle between the hairline and the eyebrows, clearly above the pupils.
3. Place the palm of your free hand on the victim's chest. Adjust your breathing to the rhythm of his breathing.
4. A person, being in a stupor, can hear and see. Therefore, speak in his ear quietly, slowly and clearly what can cause strong emotions (preferably negative ones). It is necessary by any means to achieve the reaction of the victim, to bring him out of his stupor.

Motor excitement. Sometimes the shock from a critical situation (explosions, natural disasters) is so strong that a person simply ceases to understand what is happening around him. He is not able to determine where are the enemies and where are the helpers, where is the danger and where is the salvation. A person loses the ability to think logically and make decisions, becomes like an animal rushing about in a cage.

In this situation:

1. Use the "grab" technique: from behind, put your hands under the armpits of the victim, press him to you and slightly tip him over.
2. Isolate the victim from others.
3. Massage the "positive" points. Talk in a calm voice about the feelings he is experiencing. ("Do you want to do something to stop this? Do you want to run away, hide from what is happening?")

4. Do not argue with the victim, do not ask questions, in conversation avoid phrases with a “not” particle related to undesirable actions (for example: “Do not run”, “Do not wave your arms”, “Do not shout”).
5. Remember that the victim can harm himself and others.
6. Motor excitement usually does not last long and can be replaced by nervous trembling, crying, and aggressive behavior (see help for these conditions). Aggressive behavior is one of the involuntary ways in which the human body "tries" to reduce high internal stress.

In this situation:

1. Minimize the number of people around.
2. Give the victim the opportunity to "let off steam" (for example, to speak out or "beat" the pillow).
3. Entrust him with work that involves high physical exertion.
4. Show benevolence. Even if you do not agree with the victim, do not blame him, but speak out about his actions. Otherwise, aggressive behavior will be directed at you. You can't say: "What kind of person are you!" You should say: "You are terribly angry, you want to smash everything to smithereens. Let's try to find a way out of this situation together."
5. Try to defuse the situation with funny comments or actions.
6. Aggression can be extinguished by fear of punishment:
 - if there is no goal to benefit from aggressive behavior;
 - if the punishment is severe and the likelihood of its implementation is high.
7. If you do not help an angry person, this will lead to dangerous consequences: due to a decrease in control over their actions, a person will commit rash acts, may injure himself and others.

Fear. The child wakes up at night from the fact that he had a nightmare. He is afraid of the monsters that live under the bed. Once having got into a car accident, a man cannot get behind the wheel again. An earthquake survivor refuses to go to his surviving apartment. And the one who has been subjected to violence hardly forces himself to enter his entrance. The reason for all this is fear. Panic fear, horror can induce to flee, cause numbness or, conversely, excitement, aggressive behavior. At the same time, a person controls himself poorly, does not realize what he is doing and what is happening around him.

In this situation:

1. Put the victim's hand on your wrist so that he can feel your calm pulse. This will be a signal for him: "I am here now, you are not alone!".
2. Breathe deeply and evenly. Encourage the victim to breathe in the same rhythm as you.
3. If the victim speaks, listen to him, show interest, understanding, sympathy.
4. Give the victim a light massage of the most tense muscles of the body.

Nervous trembling. After an extreme situation, uncontrollable nervous trembling appears (a person cannot stop this reaction of his own free will). This is how the body releases stress. If this reaction is stopped, then the tension will remain inside, in the body, and cause muscle pain, and in the future it can lead to the development of such serious diseases as hypertension, ulcers, etc.

In this situation:

1. It is necessary to increase the trembling.
2. Take the victim by the shoulders and shake vigorously, sharply for 10-15 seconds.

3. Keep talking to him, otherwise he may perceive your actions as an attack.
4. After the reaction is completed, it is necessary to give the victim the opportunity to rest. It is advisable to put him to sleep.
5. You can not:
 - hug the victim or hold him close;
 - cover the victim with something warm;
 - calm the victim, tell him to pull himself together.

Cry. When a person cries, substances that have a calming effect are secreted inside him. It is good if there is someone nearby with whom you can share grief. If a person holds back tears, then there is no emotional discharge, relief. When the situation drags on, internal tension can harm a person's physical and mental health.

In this situation:

1. Do not leave the victim alone.
2. Establish physical contact with the victim (take his hand, put your hand on his shoulder or back, stroke his head). Let him feel that you are near.
3. Use "active listening" techniques (they will help the victim to throw out their grief): periodically say "aha", "yes", nod your head, that is, confirm that you are listening and sympathetic; repeat after the victim passages of phrases in which he expresses his feelings; talk about your feelings and the feelings of the victim.
4. Do not try to calm the victim. Give him the opportunity to cry and speak out, "splash out" grief, fear, resentment from himself.
5. Don't ask questions, don't give advice. Your job is to listen.

Hysterics. A hysterical fit lasts a few minutes or a few hours.

In this situation:

1. Remove the audience, create a calm environment. Stay alone with the victim if it is not dangerous for you.
2. Unexpectedly perform an action that can greatly surprise (you can give a slap in the face, pour water over it, drop an object with a roar, shout sharply at the victim).
3. Speak to the victim in short phrases, in a confident tone ("Drink water", "Wash yourself").
4. After the tantrum comes a breakdown. Put the victim to sleep. Prior to the arrival of a specialist, monitor his condition.
5. Do not indulge the desires of the victim.

Emergency psychological assistance is provided to people in acute stress. This state is an experience of emotional and mental disorganization. Psychodiagnostics, psychotechniques of influence and the procedure for providing psychological assistance in extreme situations have their own specifics.

Literature:

1. А.Н.Аскарова. Психологические особенности беседы с пострадавшими в экстремальных ситуациях. Олий таълим: муаммо ва Ечимлар Республика илмий-амалий конференцияси. Илмий мақола ва тезислар тўплами. 2020 йил 25 май. 276-277 бетлар.
2. Аскарова Н. Диққат етишмаслиги синдромли ва гиперактив болаларда эмоционал соҳа коррекциясининг асосий методлари //Общество и инновации. – 2021. – Т. 2. – №. 10/S. – С. 548-554.

3. Аскарлова Н. А., Намозов М. Х. ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ СОЗДАНИЕ ПОЛОЖИТЕЛЬНЫХ ВЗАИМООТНОШЕНИЙ МЕЖДУ ВРАЧОМ И БОЛЬНЫМ //Сборники конференций НИЦ Социосфера. – Vedecko vydavatelske centrum Sociosfera-CZ sro, 2016. – №. 7. – С. 42-43.
4. Аскарлова Н. А., Қобилжонов Ж. Қ. Психологические особенности адаптационного потенциала личности больных сердечно-сосудистыми заболеваниями.
5. Крюкова М.А., Никитина Т.И., Сергеева Ю.С. Экстренная психологическая помощь: Практическое пособие. М., Изд-во НЦ ЭНАС, 2001.
6. Малкина-Пых И. Г. Экстремальные ситуации. – М.: Изд-во Эксмо, 2005. – (Справочник практического психолога). 18-24 стр.
7. Нарметова Ю. К. Особенности психокоррекционной работы с беременными женщинами //Контактная информация организационного комитета конференции. – 2016. – С. 35.
8. Нарметова Ю. К. Социально-психологический механизм организации психологических услуг в медицинских учреждениях (на примере больных с онкологическими заболеваниями) //Школа будущего. – 2015. – №. 3. – С. 148-153.
9. Нарметова Ю. К. ПСИХОСОМАТИК БЕМОРЛАРНИНГ ПСИХОЭМОЦИОНАЛ ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИ //INTEGRATION OF SCIENCE, EDUCATION AND PRACTICE. SCIENTIFIC-METHODICAL JOURNAL. – 2022. – Т. 3. – №. 2. – С. 21-28.
10. ASKAROVA N. A., IBRAGIMOVA N. N. STEPS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL ASSISTANCE IN PERSONS WITH LOSS SYNDROME //THEORETICAL & APPLIED SCIENCE Учредители: Теоретическая и прикладная наука. – 2021. – №. 9. – С. 527-529.
11. Alikhanovich M. N. et al. IMPROVEMENT OF THE METHODOLOGY FOR THE FUTURE TEACHERS'PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT //European Journal of Molecular & Clinical Medicine. – 2020. – Т. 7. – №. 9. – С. 2372-2380.
12. Abdivalievna A. N. Psychodiagnostics of children with attention deficiency syndrome and hyperactivity //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 3. – С. 2352-2355.
13. Melibayeva R.N. et al. Psychological mechanisms of development students' creative thinking //International journal of scientific & technology research. – 2020. – Т. 9. – №. 03.
14. Melibaeva R.N. Status and Prospects of Medical Psycho-Diagnostics in Uzbekistan //International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding. – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 12. – С. 555-565.
15. Narmetova Y. K. ORGANIZATION OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL SUPPORT IN THE CARDIOLOGY CLINICS //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2016. – №. 7. – С. 28-31.
16. Narmetova Y., Kuldosheva G., Bekmirov T. The Psychological Services Role in the Psychodiagnostics and Psychocorrection of Psychosomatic Patients in the Psychoemotional Situation //International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding. – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 12. – С. 249-256.